

Observation of long-range anisotropy in a vapor-deposited metallic glass (Supplemental Material)

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S1. Effects of beam size

We have conducted a test of the effects of beam size at beamline BL19LXU at the SPring-8 synchrotron facility. During this experiment, we have compared the results moving the sample in and out of focus. The beam size in focus is approximately $170\text{ nm} \times 400\text{ nm}$ full-width at half-maximum (FWHM), and about $11\text{ }\mu\text{m} \times 9\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ FWHM out of focus. It should be noted, however, that the out-of-focus beam profile is not a smooth Gaussian and may contain hot spots. Nonetheless, it is clear that the observed anisotropy is greatly reduced with the larger beam, as can be seen in Fig. S1. These images are obtained from a line scan, with a step size of $2.5\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ for in-focus and $20\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ for out-of-focus. The raw diffraction patterns are first masked (inactive area, hot pixels, and shadowing by the beam stop), then normalized by the total intensity, and finally divided by the average of the five images. Note that the color map is saturated at $\pm 4\%$, compared to $\pm 6\%$ used in the main text. These results also indicate that some averaging of the anisotropy happens already with a $\sim 170\text{ nm} \times 400\text{ nm}$ beam.

S2. Data processing method

To show that the observed anisotropy is not an artifact of the data processing method, in Fig. S2 we show the same set of data as in Fig. 2 in the

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Figure S1: Effects of beam size. The first row shows the results from a line scan of 5 images with the sample in focus, and the second row with the sample out of focus. The beam sizes on the sample are approximately $170 \text{ nm} \times 400 \text{ nm}$ FWHM and $11 \text{ }\mu\text{m} \times 9 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ FWHM, respectively, and the step sizes are $2.5 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ and $20 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, respectively. The color map is saturated at $\pm 4\%$. See text for the details on these images are calculated from the raw diffraction images.

Figure S2: Same as Fig. 2 in the main text but without subtracting the air scattering background and without normalization.

main text, but without subtracting the air scattering background and without normalization. The anisotropy is still visible, although there appear to be overall intensity fluctuations between images which partially obscure the anisotropy. These may be due to variations in sample thickness.

S3. Exclusion of radiation effects

In this section, we show evidence that the anisotropy reported in the main text is not influenced by X-ray radiation effects. Based on the lack of anisotropy in the annealed sample, as shown in Fig. 3 in the main text, we can already exclude the possibility that the anisotropy is induced by radiation. In order to test whether prolonged radiation changes the anisotropy, we performed a scan at five positions on the sample separated by $1\ \mu\text{m}$ steps. At each position, X-ray diffraction patterns are taken continuously for 60 seconds, with 1 second for each exposure. Then, we processed the data using the method described in the main text, and divided each pattern by the average of all in the scan. The results are presented in Fig. S3, from which we conclude that no obvious change in the anisotropy pattern can be seen after 60 s of X-ray exposure. Therefore, the 1 s exposure that is used to acquire the data shown in the main text should be short enough to avoid radiation-induced artifacts.

Figure S3: Investigation into possible radiation effects. A scan is performed on five consecutive positions on the sample separated by steps of $1\ \mu\text{m}$. At each position, X-ray diffraction patterns with 1 s exposure are taken continuously for 60 s. In this figure, each row represents the diffraction pattern at a different position, and the columns correspond to the diffraction pattern taken starting from 0 s, 15 s, 30 s, 45 s and 60 s, respectively. Each pattern is processed using the method described in the main text, and then divided by the average of all patterns in this scan. The color scale is the same as in Fig. S2.

S4. In- and out-of-plane anisotropy

In order to test whether there exists any macroscopic anisotropy between in-plane and out-of-plane components, we performed measurements at beamline 11-3 at the Stanford Synchrotron Radiation Lightsource (SSRL). A schematic diagram of the experimental setup is shown in Fig. S4a. The sample is placed in transmission geometry, where the angle θ between the sample plane and the horizontal plane can be changed from 60° to 140° . The X-ray photon energy is 12.7 keV, so the first diffraction maximum, around $Q = 2.84 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$, corresponds to 25.5° diffraction angle.

As can be seen in Fig. S4a, the scattering wave vectors \mathbf{Q} at different azimuthal angles χ form different angles with the sample plane. Consequently, the magnitudes of the in-plane component Q_{\parallel} and the out-of-plane component Q_{\perp} depend on χ . For example, the schematics shown in Fig. S4a uses $\theta = 60^\circ$. In this case, the component Q_{\perp} is larger at $\chi = 90^\circ$ than at $\chi = -90^\circ$. The opposite happens for $\theta = 120^\circ$. At $\theta = 90^\circ$, instead, the magnitudes Q_{\parallel} and Q_{\perp} should remain the same for all χ .

Therefore, we use 2D integration on the diffraction pattern (an example is shown in Fig. S4b), with 5° azimuthal bins. The calibration is carried out using a LaB_6 calibrant and the azimuthal integration is done with the pyFAI software [1]. We thus obtain the $I(Q)$ curve at each χ angle, from which the first maximum position, Q_{m1} , can be obtained. The results are shown in Fig. S4c. The small differences in the average Q_m value between different θ angles are due to a slight misalignment between the center of rotation and the beam position on the sample. Apart from these differences, no obvious trend can be observed, although some small modulations can be seen even in the $\theta = 90^\circ$ curve, which may be due to a varying background. Therefore, we use the $Q_{m1, \theta=90^\circ}$ curve to normalize the other curves, and the results are shown in Fig. S4d. It is clear that there is no systematic change in $Q_{m1}(\chi)$ beyond the $\pm 0.2\%$ level. Note that the out-of-plane component should be maximized at $\chi = 90^\circ$ for $\theta = 60^\circ$ and at $\chi = -90^\circ$ for $\theta = 120^\circ$ and 140° . Therefore, we conclude that there is no in- and out-of-plane anisotropy in the Q_m position beyond measurement errors.

S5. Spatial correlations of the anisotropy

In this section, we present our results on the spatial correlations of the anisotropy around the first diffraction ring in the as-deposited sample. The

Figure S4: Test of in- and out-of-plane anisotropy. (a) Experimental setup at SSRL beam line 11-3. \mathbf{k}_{in} and \mathbf{k}_{out} are incoming and outgoing wave vectors. The first diffraction maximum corresponds to around 25.5° diffraction angle. θ is the tunable angle between the sample plane and the horizontal plane. A Rayonix 225 detector is placed about 163 mm from the sample. χ is the azimuthal angle. The red vectors indicate the scattering vectors \mathbf{Q} , with an example given for the decomposition into the in-plane component \mathbf{Q}_{\parallel} and the out-of-plane component \mathbf{Q}_{\perp} . (b) An example of diffraction image. The azimuthal angle χ runs counter-clockwise, starting from -180° on the left. (c) The first maximum Q position, Q_{m1} , as a function of the azimuthal angle χ , for different sample rotations θ as shown in the legend. (d) $Q_{m1}(\chi)$ curves normalized by the curve for $\theta = 90^\circ$.

analysis is done for the same scan shown in Fig. 2 in the main text, which consists of 31×31 steps with 100 nm step size. For the analysis, we first convert the images to polar coordinates, using 2D azimuthal integration with the pyFAI software [1]. In Fig. S5, we present the same subset of images as in Fig. 2a in the main text, but in polar coordinates where the x -axis is the azimuthal angle, χ , and the y -axis is the Q value. The anisotropy around the first ring is clearly visible in these images. Then, we calculate the line profile around the first ring, $A(\chi)$, averaged over the Q range from 2.70 \AA^{-1} to 2.97 \AA^{-1} as indicated by the dashed lines. The $A(\chi)$ profiles are shown above each image. Incidentally, the images in polar coordinates also demonstrate that there are no obvious changes in the peak position regardless of the sign of the anisotropy.

Next, we calculate the correlations between the $A(\chi)$ profiles at different positions on the sample. For two positions i and j , we define their correlation $C_{i,j}$ as:

$$C_{i,j} = \frac{\frac{1}{2\pi} \int A_i(\chi) A_j(\chi) d\chi}{\left[\frac{1}{2\pi} \int A_i(\chi) d\chi \right] \left[\frac{1}{2\pi} \int A_j(\chi) d\chi \right]} - 1. \quad (\text{S1})$$

In Fig. S6a and b, we show two examples of $C_{i,j}$ fixing one of the positions (i.e., fixing i and letting j run through all steps). The fixed position is indicated by the red dot in each image. Note that it is possible for the cross-correlation ($j \neq i$) to be larger than the self-correlation ($j = i$); this can happen, for example, when the maximum and minimum of $A_j(\chi)$ appear at similar angles as those of $A_i(\chi)$, but the amplitude of the anisotropy is larger at position j than at i .

Notice that the correlations values $C_{i,j}$ are only on the order of 10^{-4} because the anisotropies are in general only a few percent. Nonetheless, the (in-plane) spatial distribution of the correlations can be easily seen in these plots. In particular, the patterns appear to have an elongated shape, and the correlation appear to oscillate somewhat periodically. This can also be seen in Fig. S6c where we plot the averaged correlations. The exact origin of these spatial correlation patterns is unknown for the moment, but it can be the subject of future works.

In Fig. S6d, we show the line-outs across the center in Δx and Δy directions. It is clear that the spatial correlation of the anisotropies can exist up to a few hundred nanometers in this sample. Note, however, that the apparent periodicity suggests that correlations may have an even longer range.

Figure S5: Processed images in polar coordinates. The images correspond to those shown in Fig. 2a in the main text, and the same color scale is used here. Shown above each image is the azimuthal profile of the anisotropy $A(\chi)$, which is averaged over the Q range from 2.70\AA^{-1} to 2.97\AA^{-1} as indicated by the dashed lines.

Figure S6: Panels (a) and (b) show two examples of the correlations $C_{i,j}$ fixing position i (indicated by the red dot), while letting j run through all steps in the scan. (c) The correlation averaged over all available positions. (d) Line-outs across the center, $(\Delta x, \Delta y) = (0, 0)$, in the two orthogonal directions.

S6. First peak positions

In this section, we quantitatively analyze the correlation (or rather, the lack thereof) between the anisotropy and the center position of the first peak, Q_{m1} . This is done in the following way. For each diffraction image, we obtain the peak position as a function of the azimuthal angle, $Q_{m1}(\chi)$. To reduce the noise, we use an azimuthal bin of 10° ; this does not lead to over-averaging because the anisotropy features are much broader, as can be seen in Fig. S5. Meanwhile, we obtain the azimuthal profile of the anisotropy, $A(\chi)$. Figure S7a presents the distribution (Q_{m1}, A) including all images in the scan and all available azimuthal angles, and in Fig. S7b we plot the average Q_{m1} value as a function of A . From these plots we conclude that there is no clear correlation between the degree of anisotropy and the position of the first peak beyond $\pm 0.1\%$ of variation in Q_{m1} .

S7. Excluding alternative explanations for the anisotropy

In this section, we provide more detailed reasoning behind the exclusion of several alternative explanations for the anisotropy in the diffraction patterns.

In general, an anisotropic diffraction could be a result of trivial geometric effects. For example, if the sample is not smooth and flat, the diffracted X-rays exiting at different positions on the surface will travel through different lengths inside the sample and experience different levels of attenuation or phase shifts, giving rise to a non-uniform pattern. However, because the attenuation length for 13 keV X-rays is around $17.9\ \mu\text{m}$ (assuming a sample density of $10.6\ \text{g}/\text{cm}^3$ [2]), $\pm 6\%$ of intensity variation would correspond to a path length difference of $\pm 1\ \mu\text{m}$. This is highly unlikely given that the sample is only about $5\ \mu\text{m}$ thick and it appears rather flat under the *in situ* microscope at the beamline. It can also be calculated that a 2π phase shift corresponds to about $8.4\ \mu\text{m}$ of path difference in the sample, and the beam is not fully coherent, so it is unlikely to explain the $\pm 6\%$ intensity variation, either. In addition, it is improbable that the unevenness always corresponds to the position of the first diffraction ring. Therefore, we exclude effects due to sample morphology as the origin of the anisotropy. Similar arguments apply against cavities (bubbles) as the cause: it is unlikely that $\sim 1\ \mu\text{m}$ of bubbles would exist across a $5\ \mu\text{m}$ sample and always on the path corresponding to the first diffraction peak.

Another possible cause of anisotropy in materials is strain. However, in a strained amorphous sample, one would expect the peak position of the

Figure S7: (a) Hexagonal bin plot of the distribution of (Q_{m1}, A) including all images and all available azimuthal angles. Shown above is the (logarithmic) color scale for the number of counts. (b) The average Q_{m1} as a function of A ; shaded region shows the standard deviation.

first diffraction ring to shift its Q position, which is indeed the observation on metallic glasses under stress [3, 4]. However, it is inconsistent with the results in this study: as can be seen in Fig. 2b in the main text and further demonstrated above, the anisotropy around the first diffraction ring does not show any shift in its Q position. Thus, we exclude strain as the main origin of the observed anisotropy.

Regarding the argument that the anisotropy may exist only at the surface and is not a property of the bulk of the material, we first note that a $\pm 6\%$ level in a $5\ \mu\text{m}$ sample means that the anisotropic “surface” region should be at least tens to hundreds of nanometers thick. In addition, we point out that, since the sample is grown by vapor deposition, the “surface” grows through the sample during the process, so we do not expect much difference between the top $\sim 100\ \text{nm}$ region below the surface and the rest of the sample.

S8. Effects of annealing: azimuthally integrated scattering intensities

In Fig. S8, we show the azimuthally integrated scattering intensity $I(Q)$ for the samples. The azimuthal integration is done using the pyFAI software [1]. The $I(Q)$ curves are averaged over runs which span at least several micrometers in each dimension, so they should represent the average structure of the samples. While the main plot shows that the curves agree in general, the upper inset shows the movement of the first peak to higher Q and a slight increase in the maximum intensity with annealing. The center positions of the first peak, Q_{m1} , are indicated by the dashed vertical lines and further listed in Table S1. Because the images are normalized by the intensity around the entire first peak (from $2\ \text{\AA}^{-1}$ to $4\ \text{\AA}^{-1}$), the increase in maximum intensity indicates a slight sharpening of the peak, which suggests a slight densification. The second peak, on the other hand, does not appear to move much, as can be seen in the lower inset as well as in Table S1: Q_{m2} increases slightly only after annealing at 639 K, when small crystals start to appear.

S9. Effects of the Ewald sphere curvature

It has been argued in the main text that the non-centrosymmetry of the diffraction patterns does not violate Friedel symmetry because the \mathbf{Q} vectors at opposite sides of the diffraction ring are not 180° apart. In other

Figure S8: Effects of annealing on the scattering intensity $I(Q)$. Upper and lower insets show details around the first and second peaks, respectively. Dashed vertical lines in the upper inset indicate the center Q position of the first peak, Q_{m1} .

Sample	Q_{m1} (\AA^{-1})	Q_{m2} (\AA^{-1})
as-deposited	2.835(1)	4.813(2)
$T_a = 602$ K	2.839(1)	4.812(2)
$T_a = 629$ K	2.839(1)	4.812(2)
$T_a = 639$ K	2.841(1)	4.815(2)

Table S1: Center position of the first peak, Q_{m1} , and the second peak, Q_{m2} , obtained from the $I(Q)$ curves in Fig. S8.

words, the Ewald sphere is sufficiently curved at the Q position of the first diffraction ring of the sample because of the finite X-ray photon energy. In order to more clearly demonstrate possible effects of this curvature, we have performed a simulation in which 300,000 crystallites are generated and their diffraction patterns calculated. Each crystallite has a face-centered cubic (FCC) structure, with one atom of the same type at each lattice site, and contains $7 \times 7 \times 7$ unit cells. The FCC lattice constant is chosen to be $a_0 = 3.83 \text{ \AA}$, so that the first allowed reflection (i.e., the (111) reflection) has $Q = 2.84 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$, very close to the value of Q_{m1} of the $\text{Pd}_{77.5}\text{Cu}_6\text{Si}_{16.5}$ sample. Thus, the size of a single crystallite is about 2.7 nm in each dimension. The orientations of the crystallites are distributed around a preferred direction such that, at this preferred orientation, one of the main axes of the FCC lattice forms a small angle with the incoming X-ray direction. When calculating the scattering intensity of the crystallites, we further assume that:

- The X-ray photon energy is 13 keV, as in the experiment. Therefore, the effect of the Ewald sphere curvature at the (111) reflection of this simulation is the same as that at the first diffraction peak of the $\text{Pd}_{77.5}\text{Cu}_6\text{Si}_{16.5}$ sample in the experiment.
- The detector is perpendicular to and centered on the incoming X-ray axis.
- We do not consider effects of the form factor. Although the form factor influences the relative intensities between different rings, it does not have any effect on the anisotropy around the same ring where Q is constant.
- The polarization factor of the X-ray scattering is not considered.
- We do not consider interference between X-rays diffracted by different crystallites. Instead, we simply sum up the scattering intensities of all crystallites.

Figure S9 shows the total scattering intensity from the crystallites. The pattern is clearly not centrosymmetric. Furthermore, the intensity maxima of the (111) and (200) reflections appear on opposite sides of the ring. These observations are due entirely to effects of the Ewald sphere curvature and the texture (preferred orientation of the crystallites).

Figure S9: Simulated diffraction pattern of 300,000 FCC crystallites. See text for details of the simulation. The part close to $Q = 0$ has been masked. The two bright rings closer to the center correspond to the (111) and the (200) reflections, as indicated in the figure. The parameters are chosen such that the (111) reflection has the same Q value as the first peak Q_{m1} of the sample.

It should be emphasized, however, that this simulation is *not* intended as a model for the $\text{Pd}_{77.5}\text{Cu}_6\text{Si}_{16.5}$ sample under study. In particular, as argued in the main text, because the anisotropy in the $\text{Pd}_{77.5}\text{Cu}_6\text{Si}_{16.5}$ sample disappears upon annealing, we may exclude the existence of crystallites in the as-deposited sample. The FCC crystallites simulated in this section are only meant as a toy model to demonstrate possible effects of the experimental geometry.

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